

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: [Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences](#)

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 130

Issue Regularity: [Monthly](#)

Review Process: [Double Blind](#)

Time to Publication: 21 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

DOI: 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: [iThenticate](#)

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

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Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

**IndexCopernicus
ICV 2020:
53.77**

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MINI REVIEW

Mediterranean Period of Islamic Medicine in Medieval

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ABSTRACT

Mediterranean is the birthplace of civilizational changes in world. There is special school of medicine in east of Islamic world which was formed by transferring Iranian medical heritage from ancient university of Jondishapur and medical sciences of India, Alexandria, Greece and Egypt. Therefore, Baghdad has arisen as a combined medical school. There is same school of medicine was established in west of Islamic world by evolutionary processes of Islamic medicine during its Mediterranean life and produced independent medical schools. Medical experience schools of ancient Cairo, Tunisia, Cordoba and Sicily transferred in Qairwan. This shows that medical development in Mediterranean world of Islamic period has been an increasing development, and Islamic medicine in the Mediterranean. Despite having Iranian roots and its origin go back to Avicenna, the founder of Islamic medicine and philosophy had a higher position than each other. It has acquired its oriental type. The medical school in the Mediterranean took place with the transfer of medicine from the first house of wisdom in the Islamic world to the second house of wisdom, which was built in Qairwan by Aghlabids state. The reality of Mediterranean period of Islamic medicine and its physical role in history of world medicine played by House of Wisdom (Beit al-Hakme) Qairwan in the last stages of its development has prepared the collection of Islamic medical knowledge produced in Beit al-Hikma in Baghdad for final development by combining Latin teachings. By Transfer of Roman and Byzantine; medical knowledge from the Latin world to the Islamic world, which was a major milestone in the history of world medicine in southern Europe was made in Andalusia on the Iberian Peninsula, setting the stage for the latest evolution of medicine. A vast body of medical knowledge was transferred from North Africa and Andalusia to Europe (Salerno Italy) at the beginning of the European Renaissance.

INTRODUCTION

Geographical distribution of Islamic medicine in the Mediterranean Byzantine and African Empires

Africa in its broadest sense was used before the arrival of Islam in the West and was occupied by Byzantine and Rome Empire. The strategic position of Africa from Barqa (in Lybia) to Tangier (in Morocco) in terms of the domination of the Mediterranean and due to its rich economic resources has always been of special interest to the Byzantine Empire [1]. The Romans paid special attention to Africa and Africa was one of the great states with the blessing of Roman Empire, from which a large part of Roman government's income was provided. This region, which is now part of North Africa, has long been the centre of human medical education in ancient times In the Middle Ages it became the centre of Islamic medicine. The Iberian Peninsula, which was called the Andalusian Islamic Peninsula, was founded by innovators in a region that formed the independent school of Andalusian medicine in southern Europe. Andalusia is one of the scattering points of Mediterranean medicine in southern Europe and Egypt in northern Africa. The question is whether there was only one transfer in this region. The transfer of ancient medical knowledge to the middle Ages and then its transfer to Europe took place in the Renaissance, and the hypothesis is that the School of Islamic Medicine in North Africa and Andalusia was a genuine school Rather; it was the initiative, establishment, and development of medicine

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DOI: 10.37871/jbres1438

Submitted: 11 March 2022

Accepted: 30 March 2022

Published: 31 March 2022

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OPEN ACCESS

Keywords

- Mediterranean
- Medicine
- Medieval

GENERAL SCIENCE

COMMUNITY HEALTH

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 3 - MARCH, 2022

and the new school in medicine. The article examines the transfer, development, and evolution of medicine on both the eastern and western Mediterranean sides of the Middle Ages by Islamic civilization.

Medical activity of Islamic civilization in the Eastern Mediterranean in the middle ages

House of Wisdom (Beit al-Hikma) Qirwan, translation movement and originality of Islamic civilization: One of the periods of science transfer from antiquity to medieval is establishment of Science Translation and Transfer Centre. The first House of Wisdom was established in the capital of the Caliphate of Baghdad, with the aim of transmitting the teachings of ancient period. The truth of the House of Wisdom was the place of origin of ancient scientific centres to the middle Ages. The second house of wisdom in the Islamic world after Baghdad was established in Qairwan. The duties of this House of Wisdom were translation, transfer, composition and development of sciences and knowledge. Although he was present in the Maghrib conquest of Khorasan, the development of Islamic and Iranian sciences and knowledge in the Maghreb House of Wisdom was also done by Iranian elements. Mathematics is one of the Iranian scientists whose name is associated with the House of Wisdom in Qairvan [2]. The emergence and development of science and education of the majority period was due to the Byzantine and Greek sciences and education in Africa, as well as the transfer of science and education and the science-seeking movement and production of knowledge from the East (Baghdad) to Africa; The movement of translating and founding the "House of Wisdom" in the Dar al- Baghdad Calif was also imitated by many rulers in Qairwan, and the second House of Wisdom in the Islamic world was established in this city by many rulers; The most important mission of this House of Wisdom was to compile and translate Latin and Greek books, especially in the field of medicine into Arabic; Several of the most eminent rulers, who were fluent in Latin themselves, played a significant role in this; But in fact, the mass migration of Iranian scientists to Qayravan had a great impact on the establishment of the Qayravan House of Wisdom.

Transfer of medicine from first house of wisdom in Islamic world to second house of wisdom by Iranian: Establishment of Qairwan Medical School with the migration of Iranian doctors from Baghdad is one of the most scientific migration in history .The ancient heritage of medicine was collected from Jundishapur, the medical centre of the Sassanid Empire, and from India, Alexandria, and Greece in Baghdad, and a new form and stage of the development of post-medieval medicine was formed in Baghdad. The flood of Iranian scientists reached Qairvan. And the biggest physical transfer in the history of world medicine took place. They paid special attention to medicine as well as physicians, and brought many skilled physicians and medical books from Baghdad and Egypt, one of them

is Ishaq Ibn Sulayman, a Jew, was one of the first Iranian physicians to enter Qayrawan from Baghdad [3].

Physician as a Body jurists: Medicine and physicians took on a new shape and personality in accordance with Islamic civilization in the Qairwan medical school, so that a special class emerged among scientists who became known as the jurists of the body due to the new medical knowledge presented in the Qairwan House of Wisdom. The result of medical education in Africa was the emergence of a large number of physicians in Africa and the training of people who were largely familiar with traditional medicine and various medicines and were known as body jurists [4].

Special facility for treatment and care of special patients in Qairwan Medical School: The Africa School of Medicine in New structure for treatment and nursing of epidemic and special patients who should be kept away from the general public and kept in quarantine. There are any special place in some city of Africa as Sousse and Tunisia were built The "majority" built specially architecturally special hospital facilities throughout Africa on the outskirts of major cities; The first "demneh" was built by Ziadullah I around Qirwan; Demneh Sousseh was built around the city of Sousseh by Ibrahim II and Demneh Sefakhs belt in 235 AH [5].

Ibn Jazar Medical School the symbol of medicine of west Mediterranean Sea: Ibn Jazar Qirwani 285-369, withdrew from politics, he wrote a book on the history of the Fatimid state A special school in the science of "Siddhala" was founded by the famous Fatimid physician , Ahmad Ibn Jazar; His book "Zad Al-Masafar" has been used in medical circles for centuries in the science of Siddhala, and the science of pharmacology has been translated into Italia by his work. He is the founder of Pediatrics and his book is How to Care for a Child from Fetus to Early Childhood. The most important book of his is about observing health and maintaining health while traveling. Napoleon accompanied the book on his trip to Egypt and acted on it [6].

Al-Hashaah Compassion is foundation of medicine in Islamic West: Al-Hashish from Pedanius Discords big heritage of ancient was translated from Greek into Arabic by Istifan Ibn Basil in the middle of the third century, and its re-translation in Andalusia highlighted the Greek lineage in the Andalusian alphabet; According to Ibn al-Joljol, the previous translation was incomplete and the new translation was complete [7].

Islamic medicine in Zirids state era - Development and continuation of Qirwan medical school: Zirids period is the age of development of medical sciences. Qairwan Medical School in Zirids was ruled by any Jew physicians in. African Constantine (480 AH), born in Carthage, was also an African physician and a major factor in the transfer of medicine from Africa to Europe [8].

Medicine in Age of AL- Mohads Empire: The Movahedi period is also a period of fundamental change in the field of

"medicine". These people acted as a special physician for the AL- Mohads caliphs. Ibn Rushd, the author of the book general in medicine (Al-Kaliyat Fi Al-Tib), has proposed innovative theories in the field of "medicine" in this book. Ibn Rushd's views on "music, the goal of music as pushing human beings to balance. The "hospital" of Morocco was the place of treatment of all kinds of diseases and had a large number of doctors and was unique in the world in its time. During this period, there established a special organization of physicians, which was part of the administrative organization of AL- Mohads government [9].

Medicine in Marinyds state period: Medicine in the Marini era is a continuation of the classical achievements of Islamic medicine, which were available in medical centers during the aL-mohads era, and on the other hand, it is the efforts of the Andalusians who were welcomed by the people of the Maghreb. Including the physician Ahmad ibn Ashar Ansari Andalusian, who died in 1764, went from Andalusia to the Maghreb. After traveling to its cities, he settled in Sala and was treated. He became well known as the physician of Sidi Ibn Ashar. African Lyon has a report on Fez doctors and how they produce medicine. In the tenth century AH, Fez had 157 places and shops for making, selling and making medicine in Attari market. Lyon also has widespread criticism of the prevalence of popular medicine in Fez and the prevalence of superstition in Fez in the field of medicine [10].

Medical science of the Hafsids kingdom period: Hafsidsis is an end of evolution of physician in Africa, and Tunisia Capital of Hafsid kingdom is centre of medical book in east and west of Mediterranean Sea; Tunisia became the most important bridge for transfer medicine to Europe. Any Hafsids phis Iain were special doctor in court of European kingdom.

Advancement of Medicine in Spain in Islamic Period: Andalusia is end point of evolution of Islamic medicine and by means of migration from east made it centre of research and initiatives of Islamic civilization in medicine.

Role of Razes and Avenecia in Andalusian Medicine Foundation: Andalusia has no brilliant history in medicine was one of sciences that developed significantly in Andalusian, like medicine in other parts of the Islamic world, has an Iranian origin by works of Razes and Avicenna. Avicenna's influence on Andalusian medicine is such that considered his birthplace to be Cordoba.

Development and innovation of Ibn Zuhr in Andalusia: Abd al-Malik ibn Zuhr (557 AH / 1162 AD), using the knowledge of his predecessors, especially Galen, completed his medical knowledge by codifying his clinical observations; He discovered myocardial infarction and used tracheostomy (incision of the trachea for search and sampling) and introduced artificial nutrition.

Zahrawi (ALBUCASIS) founder of surgery and his place

in history of medicine: Abu al-Qasim Zahrawi (325 AH - 407 AH / 936 - 1016), born in the city of Al-Zahra, was the first founder of the science of "surgery" in world to invent a special method of surgery that relied on sensory experience and observation; He compiled the book Al-Tasrif has described 107 cases of surgical instruments that he uses.

There are 28 manuscripts of this book in the world and it has been translated into French and Latin and so far dozens of articles, books and congresses have been compiled and written about him. He is considered to be the first person in surgery to prevent bleeding during surgery and has been considered an innovator and pioneer in many fields. Among the inventions of surgical instruments, and the invention of printing devices, he is considered a thousand years before John, the German Gutenberg. He was successful for the first time in the history of orthodontic dentistry with gold thread and jaw and tooth surgery.

Ahmad Ghafghi Andalusian pharmacist

Abu Ja'far Ahmad Ghafiqi has been mentioned as one of the pioneers of the new science of "eye pathology. A physician and researcher who made medicine by searching and researching in nature and combined Arabic, Greek and Roman researches and criticized and developed them.

Pharmacology (Sidaleh) in Andalusia, transfer, development of origin

There is still much debate as to whether the origins of Latin medicine entered Islamic civilization from Andalusia or from the Maghreb, as it is certain. But there is in Ibn Jazar's medical heritage, the physician of the Fatimid government, who used Descorides's translation of Maghreb as his instructor, five hundred plants have been registered. With this amount of pharmacology, they soon added to the ancient heritage. Muslims are the founders of pharmacology in the middle Ages. One of the most important achievements of the Muslims in Andalusia is in the field of pharmacology ("Siddhala"), knowledge of plant properties). This science in andalusia, has been researched by orientalists. Its origins go back to the Muslim retrieval and development of the most advanced text of medieval pharmacology; Discorded the origin of medicine was first translated into Arabic in Cordoba and reported in Cairo; Among some Jewish and Muslim physicians; it was under the supervision of Nicholas the Monk, sent by Armanius to Nasser's court in 340 AH. This was translated into both Latin and Greek. According to another account, in the middle of the third century, the book Al-Hashaish was translated from Greek into Arabic by Istifan Ibn Basil in the House of Wisdom of Qairwan, and its re-translation in Andalusia highlighted the Greek lines in the Andalusian style; According to Ibn Joljol, the previous translation was incomplete and the new translation was complete; of the book on the remembrance of the medicine that is not mentioned by Discords.

Medicine in Eastern Mediterranean of Egypt and the evening of Fazemian government:

The science of medicine in the Fatimid era: Al-Azhar and medicine: The Fatimid era is the glorious period of Islamic medicine and the stage of integration, evolution, innovation, production and copying of works in medicine – and the greats of Islamic medicine such as Ibn Rezvan shone in it. Al-Azhar is one of the centers for the development of Fatimid medicine. Ibn Abi Asbiyah has mentioned 24 physicians of the Fatimid period and several chief physicians of this era with their works and deeds. At the head of the medical organization was the Chief of Medicine.

Ophthalmology Epidemic: The Fatimid period is the age of final progress in the knowledge of the eye and its functions, and its ophthalmology and surgery. The most authentic Muslim ophthalmologist in contains detailed descriptions of eye diseases and their treatment.

The second type: maintaining health and environment and climate: Ali Ibn Rezwan: fighting the epidemic. The issue of weather in the cities of Egypt is the main problem of Egyptian medicine. And for this reason, books on Islamic prevention in water, food and air were written, and hygiene is one of the most important topics in Egyptian medicine.

The head of the Egyptian physician Ibn Rezwan 1067 AD His treatise on preserving health in repelling the harms of the body against the Egyptian plague is important. He wrote a scientific letter in seven parts to Ibn Rezwan. In a part of the letter, he criticized the Egyptian method of medicine and accused Ibn Rezwan. Competition in writing works in the climate in Egypt in the works of Ibn Jami 'such as Al-Arshad for the interests of the souls and bodies and the treatise on the nature of Alexandria and the state of the air and the winds and the syntax of Zalak.

CONCLUSION

A tangible result of the study of the periods and courses of medicine in the Middle Ages in the Islamic West in Spain, Portugal and North Africa of the Islamic period shows that twenty-four governments in this operation have tried to

transfer medical knowledge from ancient times to the Middle Ages and a new system They created medical knowledge from the composition and development of the ancient medical reagent, which is still used, and at the beginning of the Renaissance, it provided the ground for medical development in the first European medical universities. And established a genuine and independent medical school that has established schools and is like the Canon of Avicenna, which has been applicable in medical education in different societies since the beginning of the Renaissance. It was the second book after the Bible five hundred years ago. It was previously translated and published in Latin in Europe. And the Islamic states have been with the scientific policy of transferring and developing sciences, especially medicine, and there has been a special system for medical management in their administrative apparatus. And every government is known for being an innovator and a scientist in medicine. The Aghlebids state is known for establishing the House of Science and Transfer of Sciences and the Fatimids state and Zirids state by Ibn Jazar, the founder of School of Pediatrics, and the AL-Mohads state by Averroes, the end of Islamic medicine, and Hafsids state by IBN Andras Avicenna II. And in Andalusia societies, Ibn zuhr (1168 AD) Zahrawi (ALBUCASIS) is known as the founder of surgery and Ibn Wafid is the famous founder of pharmacology.

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